

BUILDING BRIDGES TO OPEN ACCESS

Paths to Institutional Rights Retention in Europe 2024

Jon Treadway
Ignasi Labastida i Juan
Iva Melinščak Zlodi
Vanessa Proudman

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Authors

Ignasi Labastida i Juan, University of Barcelona

Iva Melinščak Zlodi, University of Zagreb

Vanessa Proudman, SPARC Europe

Jon Treadway, Great North Wood Consulting

Reviewers

Barbara Stratton, Stephen Wyber

Editing and proofreading

Stephen Wyber

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ABOUT THE AUTHORS

Ignasi Labastida i Juan

Rector's Delegate for Open Science, University of Barcelona

Ignasi Labastida is the Rector's Delegate for Open Science at the University of Barcelona and a member of the Open Science Working Group at the Spanish Rectors' Conference. He also chairs the Info and Open Access Group at the League of European Research Universities (LERU). Since 2013, he has extensive experience working with copyright and Open Access licences, leading Creative Commons in Spain.

Iva Melinščak Zlodi

Scholarly Communication & E-Resources Librarian, University of Zagreb, Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences

Iva Melinščak Zlodi is the Chair of the SPARC Europe Board. She is a scholarly communication and e-resources librarian at the University of Zagreb Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, responsible for institutional repository development, support in electronic publishing, providing electronic resources, information literacy education, and bibliometric monitoring of research output.

Vanessa Proudman Director, SPARC Europe

Vanessa Proudman is the Director of SPARC Europe. She has 20 years of international experience working on Open Access, Open Science, Open Culture and Open Education with many leading universities and libraries worldwide from over 20 countries. She is an experienced project and programme manager of European Commission projects for universities, their libraries, for foundations and led a department of information and IT at a UN-European region research organisation for well over 10 years.

Jon Treadway Director, Great North Wood Consulting

Jon Treadway is the Director of Great North Wood Consulting. Jon has over 20 years' experience working on strategic and policy projects for organisations in the research sector and creative industries. Jon specialises in navigating complex problems, bringing together quantitative and qualitative analysis, and delivering actionable outputs.

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KNOWLEDGE RIGHTS 21

Knowledge Rights 21 is focused on bringing about changes in legislation and practice across Europe that will strengthen the right of all to knowledge. It is built on a conviction that access to knowledge is essential for education, innovation and research, and that everyone in society should have the possibility to access and use information in both analogue and digital forms. This, in turn, will help Europe deliver on its economic, social, environmental and democratic potential.

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Dr Per Pippin Aspaas, Senior Academic Librarian, Universitet i Tromsø (UiT), Norway

Andrew Barker, Director of Library Services & Learning Development, Lancaster University, United Kingdom

Dr. Maja Bogataj Jančič, LL.M., LL.M., Open Data and Intellectual Property Institute ODIPI, www.odipi.si, Slovenia; KR21 National and Regional Coordinator, Slovenia and the Western Balkans

Niamh Brennan, Programme Manager for Research Informatics, Trinity Innovation and Enterprise, Trinity College Dublin, Ireland

Darco Jansen, Manager Open Science & Open Access, Universities of the Netherlands, The Netherlands

Dr. Mojca Kotar, Assistant Secretary General, University Office of Library Services, University of Ljubljana, Slovenia

Kirsty Langstadt, Director of Library, Learning, Archives and Wellbeing, University of York, United Kingdom

Dr Ana Lazarova, Chief Assistant Professor, Sofia University St. Kliment Ohridski, Bulgaria; KR21 National Coordinator, Bulgaria

Frances Madden, Assistant Head of Research Services, Technological University Dublin, Ireland

Silvana Mangriaracina, Librarian, CNR Bologna, Italy

Lionel Maurel, Scientific Deputy Director, Open Science, Scientific Publishing and Research Data, CNRS Humanities & Social Sciences, France

Anna Molino, Librarian, CNR Pisa, Italy

Ginevra Peruginelli, Legal Researcher, Institute of Legal Informatics and Judicial Systems, Italy

Susan Reilly, Director, Irish Research Electronic Library (IREL), Maynooth University, Ireland

Milica Ševkušić, Librarian at the Institute of Technical Sciences of the Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts, Serbia; EIFL Open Access Programme Country Coordinator, Serbia

Sarah Thompson, Associate Director (Content and Open Research), University of York, United Kingdom

Tatjana Timotijević, Head of Department of Scientific Information, National Library of Serbia and Country Coordinator of Serbian Library Consortium for Coordinated Acquisition (KOBSON), Serbia

Ophélie Wang, Librarian, Bibliothèque interuniversitaire Cujas, France; KR21 National Coordinator, France

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report, *Building Bridges to Open Access: Paths to Institutional Rights Retention in Europe*, presents case studies from ten European countries, illustrating a diverse landscape of progress, challenges, and strategic approaches. It features initiatives in Bulgaria, Finland, France, Ireland, Italy, the Netherlands, Norway, Serbia, Slovenia, and the UK.

Section One is aimed at the leaders of research institutions and anyone who is considering an institutional rights retention policy, regardless of their specific responsibilities or the country in which they work.

Section Two offers an overview of the themes and trends emerging from the case studies and the progress seen to date. It focuses particularly on the interplay between legislation and policy development, the response to policies being developed and implemented, and the benefits that have so far emerged.

Section Three presents the case studies in detail.

Among the case studies featured in the report, the UK and Norway feature institutions that were in the first wave of those developing policies in 2022 and since 2022. The others feature a range of different approaches to policy development:

- Finland and Italy are fostering collaborative efforts, focusing on education and training to advance institutional policies despite the hurdles of legal reform.
- France and the Netherlands have introduced Secondary Publishing Rights (SPR), and institutions are now working to raise awareness on rights. A coherent institutional policy response is emerging to ensure that the full benefits can be realised.
- Ireland and Slovenia are adopting a holistic strategy, balancing institutional policy adoption with legal reform discussions.
- Bulgaria has recently enacted legislative changes, but institutions must now implement institutional policies to capitalise on these reforms.
- Serbia is considering legislative reform to support long-standing discussions on rights retention.

To those considering how to make progress in their own institution or particular environment, we recommend the following:

- Map the landscape to understand the legal and institutional factors at play.
- Prioritise progress over perfection, recognising that incremental changes can yield meaningful results.
- Build alliances by connecting with interested parties across institutions and sectors.
- Seek sound legal advice to navigate risks and optimise policy design.

Moving forward, the case studies show a variety of available pathways to adopting rights retention policies. While legal reforms – in particular the introduction of Secondary Publishing Rights – provide a valuable legal backstop and impetus for change, progress on the ground also relies on clear institutional policies to ensure rights are understood and utilised. Unavoidably, legislative reform also takes time, and faster progress can often be achieved through institutional policy development where leadership and collaboration enable it.

The examples from Norway and the UK illustrate how a rights retention policy can yield high levels of Open Access, and other examples show the benefits of adapting strategies to legislative reform depending on the context in different countries. Ultimately, there is no universal blueprint, but the experiences detailed here show the phase of rapid progress that started in 2022 and 2023 continues in a broad range of contexts, continuing to facilitate Open Access to research.

INTRODUCTION

The [Knowledge Rights 21](#) (KR21) programme was founded in 2021 and is funded by the Arcadia Foundation. KR21 is committed to reforming copyright legislation and practices and to ensure access to research, education, and cultural resources in the digital age.

[Project Retain](#), a KR21 workstream led by SPARC Europe, has sought to accelerate the uptake of rights retention and open licensing to enable researchers to share their work openly.

Phase One of Project Retain sought to identify broad trends and patterns. We combined qualitative and quantitative analysis to offer insights into and engage with a wide range of stakeholder groups. This resulted in the June 2023 report [Opening Knowledge: Retaining Rights and Licensing in Europe 2023](#). The report made the following recommendations to institutional policymakers seeking to augment their existing policies with elements to promote rights retention:

- Seek expert legal advice to ensure that appropriate rights are retained by the institution and employee/author under local copyright and contract law.
- Consider how to make an approach most effective given the prevailing Open Access models and publishing cultures; the [Good practices for University Open Access](#) policies is a valuable resource for doing this.
- Design strategies to maximise approval from researchers, including involvement in policy-making, awareness-raising campaigns and training.
- Provide resources to support researchers who are being required to retain rights; at minimum, this should be specific guidance on how to meet the requirements being placed on them. Ideally it should be staff with the responsibility to provide advice and support communications and negotiations with publishers.
- Work with networks of institutions that they consider peers to pool expertise and capacity.
- Showcase policies and approaches locally, regionally and nationally to build awareness and understanding.

Phase Two of Project Retain began in the summer of 2024. It aims to understand better how rights retention policies are developing across a range of European countries.

We are publishing a series of ten case studies based on interviews with advocates for rights retention reform in ten European countries, coordinated with KR21 National Coordinators in each country. The case studies highlight different approaches and rates of progress, and make up the core of this report.

Accompanying these case studies, the report offers two differing perspectives in *Sections One* and *Two* that will be of interest and practical help to those involved in discussions about rights retention across Europe.

Section One is aimed at the leaders of research institutions and anyone who is considering an institutional rights retention policy, regardless of their specific responsibilities or the country in which they work. It draws on the case studies to offer guidance on whether and how to introduce a policy, structured around common areas of interest:

- What form could a policy take?
- What factors should be considered?
- What are the benefits of a rights retention policy?
- How to persuade an institution to develop a policy, and how to go about developing it?

It concludes with some simple recommendations that we hope are of real use to those seeking to develop a policy:

- Seek to map out the different factors at play in their environment that will influence the extent and nature of policy.
- Do not seek perfection. No such thing exists, and a great deal of progress can be made even in difficult environments and unfavourable legal jurisdictions.
- Seek other interested parties, within and outside your institution, that can help pool resources and accelerate progress.
- Seek good and creative legal advice. It will help you understand your options and the risks that need to be addressed.

Section Two complements *Section One* and offers an overview of the themes and trends emerging from the case studies and the progress seen to date. It focuses particularly on the interplay between legislation and policy development, the response to policies being developed and implemented, and the benefits that have so far emerged.

Institutional rights retention policies offer a mechanism to safeguard researchers’ rights while representing a highly promising route through which institutions can facilitate Open Access to scholarly outputs. While legislative reform can complement and act as a foundation for rights retention work, it takes years to achieve. Institutional policy development and commitment to support researchers exercising their rights can allow institutions to take action now and help facilitate greater Open Access to researchers’ work. There is considerable variation in the approaches and policy types emerging. This flexibility is a strength of the approach and should encourage others to develop their own initiatives.

SUMMARY OF CASE STUDIES

The case studies are published in full in *Section Three* of the report. We would encourage you to read them. They are deliberately designed to be concise and accessible and offer valuable insights into the distinct elements in each situation.

[Bulgaria](#) – A network of non-governmental organisations and librarian groups has taken a structured approach to seeking reform through legislation and institutional policy change. The initial reform was driven by Members of Parliament with backgrounds in research, Open Science, and civil society. The result has been a pioneering staged introduction of Secondary Publishing Rights and Obligations. Focus has now moved to developing institutional rights retention policies and accompanying support mechanisms for researchers; such policies are essential to ensure that the legislative reform can have its desired effects.

[Finland](#) – The Finnish University Libraries Network (FUN) has sought to learn from experiences in the UK, Norway and other Scandinavian countries. There is little appetite for legislative reform, and no clear existing legal basis for institutional rights retention policies. As such, their approach has been to build support across a network of institutions, from rectors and other stakeholders, with many research organisations prepared to move together and planning to adopt institutional rights retention policies together before the end of 2025.

[France](#) – Secondary Publishing Rights are already established in French law, and institutional policies have been adopted with recommendations around rights retention. This has led to a tangible increase in materials being made openly accessible. However, there has not been widespread adoption of policies which mandate the retention of rights by authors or that they adopt specific behaviours. Attempts to bring in policies of this type have proved controversial. As such, further reform efforts are focused on training and awareness-raising - seeking to ensure researchers and librarians understand that rights retention will not infringe academics' freedom to choose where they publish.

[Ireland](#) – The 'Secondary Rights, Copyright, Open Access, Institutional Policies, and Rights Retention' initiative (SCOIR) in Ireland has been funded by Ireland's National Open Research Forum (NORF) with engagement from KR21. SCOIR is pursuing legislative reform to allow researchers to deposit manuscripts in parallel with the development of institutional policies that support rights retention. This twin-track approach has been made possible due to the range of expertise at the initiative's disposal through its expert advisory panel and own leadership. It comes at a fortuitous time as many institutions are seeking to renew or review their Open Access policies or, in the case of several of the Technological Universities, to introduce them for the first time.

[Italy](#) – Right2Pub was a time-limited Italian initiative that was launched in late 2023. It aimed to strengthen awareness of and action for researchers' rights to publish and the reuse of their own work. Right2Pub brought together the Institute of Legal Informatics and Judicial Systems (IGSG), libraries within the National Research Council (CNR), and Creative Commons Italy. Right2Pub followed three phases: researching the scientific community's awareness of rights and copyright, developing targeted training and resources, and advocating for legislative reform. Right2Pub's work is now being carried forward by various routes that continue to expand training, call for legal reform, and encourage institutional mandates that support authors' rights retention.

[Netherlands](#) – The Taverne Amendment (2015) grants researchers a Secondary Publishing Right for short scientific works. This has been actively implemented since 2019 by a coalition of universities encouraging researchers to take advantage of their rights. However, variations in copyright ownership and rights retention practice persist, associated with different interpretations and ways of working in different institutions, and funder requirements which go beyond what the Taverne Amendment anticipated. Working groups of The Universities of the Netherlands are seeking to resolve this through a combination of dialogue, coordinated action and providing clarity over the differences between institutions.

[Norway](#) – All research institutions in Norway now have rights retention policies and are beginning to see their impact. The case study focuses on the University of Tromsø – The Arctic University of Norway (UiT), which now sees >96% of its researchers' journal articles made Open Access, with the rights retention policy instrumental in extending this to the 10-15% of researchers for whom other routes are not viable. UiT's policy (and those in other institutions) has been well received by the research community and forms one strand of the institution's active pursuit of its strategy of being the Open Access pioneer of the North.

[Serbia](#) – Under Serbia's copyright legislation, institutions hold economic rights to the outputs of publicly-funded research for five years. Many institutions have adopted Open Access policies emphasising this right, and encouraging the use of author addenda to achieve it. However, researchers often transfer rights to publishers, undermining this provision. Legislation is under consideration to introduce a Secondary Publishing Right for researchers, but progress is slow and support is not yet widespread. Attention is also focused on strengthening the national Open Science policy by requiring authors to act in accordance with copyright law.

[Slovenia](#) – Slovenia has adopted a comprehensive strategic and political framework for Open Science. The *Scientific Research and Innovation Activities Act* (2021) introduced legal obligations about retention of rights, which was extended by a governmental *Decree on Open Science* that set out a framework through which the Act would be implemented. An *Action Plan for Open Science* is providing financial and structural support for more effective implementation of principles of Open Science. As part of this Action Plan, the SPOZNAJ project aims to align research activities at the institutional level with principles embedded in Slovenian law. Different institutions are taking different approaches; notably, the University of Ljubljana, Slovenia’s largest research institution, adopted an institutional policy that mandates authors to apply Open Science obligations in full. Further work to train and educate researchers, and legislative reform that would introduce Secondary Publishing Rights, are currently under consideration.

[United Kingdom](#) – the N8 partnership of research-intensive institutions in the North of England was the first coalition of organisations to introduce rights retention policies in the UK, alongside a number of other institutions doing so individually in 2022 and 2023. The collaboration was rooted in existing structures that facilitated coordination of policies and activities across libraries. This allowed the institutions to move quickly when they may not have done so individually, to move at different speeds where necessary, and to pool support resources. Publisher reaction has been minimal and researcher adoption has been smooth due to the preparatory work done by the institutions. It is still early, but the policies have had a measurable impact on materials being made Open Access.

SECTION ONE: WHAT TO CONSIDER WHEN DEVELOPING A RIGHTS RETENTION POLICY

This section is for leaders of research institutions and anyone who is considering whether and how to develop an institutional rights retention policy, regardless of their specific responsibilities or the country in which they work. We have grouped the section around common areas of interest and questions that are routinely asked by those considering policies.

WHAT FORM COULD A POLICY TAKE?

Dimensions along which policies can vary

During the Phase One of Project Retain, we adopted the following definition for an institutional rights retention policy.

An expressed position setting out the practice of retaining sufficient rights for academic works produced by an institution's researchers to make the work openly accessible and reusable immediately.

This is a broad definition. It was deliberately chosen to accommodate the breadth of policies under consideration and development at the time.

It continues to be useful because there is still a wide variation in what institutions consider.

There is no 'perfect' rights retention policy, and adopting an overly rigid definition or unachievable goals can prevent substantial progress. However, there is real value in implementing policies that make more content openly accessible and can clarify the rights and obligations of researchers, even if these are not as comprehensive or ambitious as some of the policies in different jurisdictions. The policy approaches already implemented in the UK and Norway, and actively being pursued by institutions in Finland, France and Slovenia illustrate how different approaches and progress can be achieved.

In Phase One of the project, we highlighted a number of dimensions along which policies varied. The following remain key considerations during Phase Two:

Policy scope	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • May be a standalone policy or incorporated into broader policies covering Open Access, publishing, or intellectual property.
Nature of mandate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some policies establish a right for institutions or authors, some mandate researchers to exercise or retain specific rights, some make recommendations to researchers, some policies only offer guidance for researchers seeking to meet a funder mandate. • Researchers may be able to opt-out of the policy if they deem that they are unable to publish their research effectively.
Content covered	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • May cover only journal articles, a wider range of written scholarly output, or non-written outputs from research including data and software. • May require an Author Accepted Manuscript or Version of Record.
Authors covered	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • May cover just employed faculty members conducting research, or extended to non-faculty, including postgraduate students.
Open licensing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • May require CC-BY, some other combination of CC licences, or may not require any specific licence type.

The following points are worthy of note regarding how different dimensions play out in practice.

- There can be considerable variation in policies developed by institutions participating in the same collaborative initiatives to pool resources and establish common ground. The N8 collaboration in the UK demonstrates this well, as do the cross-institutional approaches facilitated by the Finnish University Libraries Network (FUN) and the Universities of the Netherlands. The SCOIR initiative in Ireland and Right2Pub in Italy are examples of broad initiatives involving multiple stakeholders.

- Most policies in place or under consideration only cover journal articles, although some also include monographs. Coverage of broader research outputs remains a goal but is often more challenging. The approach to reform taken in Slovenia leaves open the possibility that different types of output may be included in future, while the collaboration in the Netherlands is seeking a pragmatic approach according to what is possible for different research outputs in different institutions.
- Mandating CC-BY licences for research outputs remains challenging. In most cases, institutional policymakers pursue a mix of other CC licence types or recommend using the most open licence possible. Examples of different approaches may be found in Slovenia, Bulgaria and Norway.

WHAT FACTORS SHOULD BE CONSIDERED?

This section aims to provide a non-exhaustive list of the most significant factors to consider when developing a rights retention policy. The recommendations from the June 2023 report [Opening Knowledge: Retaining Rights and Licensing in Europe 2023](#) focused on the need to seek legal advice, consider existing internal policies and resources, and build alliances with networks of peer institutions. These remain very important considerations (see below under *Internal factors*), but the case studies that accompany this report have been chosen to highlight how a very broad set of different external and internal factors are affecting the approaches taken, and notably the type of policies under consideration.

Most of the case studies present national initiatives or involve collaborations between multiple partners. Such approaches are well-suited to helping individual institutions make progress, as well as offering insights for individual institutions.

External factors

- **Legislation** plays a crucial role in shaping approaches to developing policies and the policies put in place:
 - **Copyright laws** governing the initial ownership of and subsequent (related) rights in copyright materials directly affect how institutions can claim or manage rights over scholarly works. These laws determine whether researchers or their institutions hold the primary rights to their publications and the extent to which institutions have rights as employers of researchers. Some institutions' policies voluntarily assign their employer's copyright in some or all types of works made for hire or in the course of employment by their staff to the actual authors. Legislation also governs what rights authors and publishers, etc. have and the extent to which other considerations, such as statutory exceptions, can override their rights. The law also covers some matters concerning authors' contracts with publishers. However, legislation in the EU generally assumes that authors automatically retain and cannot assign their personal moral rights in a work elsewhere, even if they do not own the copyright because they had assigned it elsewhere or the work was made for hire. However, in some countries they may be able to voluntarily waive their moral rights. Reform to copyright law has progressed in Bulgaria, while alternative approaches have been pursued in Italy, Serbia and Slovenia due to the challenges of reforming copyright law. Despite the European Union copyright *acquis* that establishes an EU-wide copyright framework, which still has a legacy in UK copyright law since Brexit, differences in national copyright laws and the ways in which they are implemented are key factors behind the approaches being explored and adopted in France, the Netherlands, Serbia and the UK.
 - **Contracts** - Additionally, it is worth noting that, unless national legislation should mandate otherwise, the general principles of intellectual property ownership established in law and of general contract law apply. These already provide an environment in which, by negotiating the publishing contracts offered to them, authors, or their institution where it owns the rights, may be able, for example, to not assign their copyright and some or all of their existing related rights (and future rights) to the publisher on an exclusive basis either for a fixed period. Alternatively, they can provide for reversion of rights to

the original rights holder when the work is out of commerce, for example to allow for re-publication or making available elsewhere, e.g. by Open Access (see Publishing Culture below for Transformative Agreements). Alternatively, rights holders may instead choose to offer the publisher an exclusive or non-exclusive licence to publish on similar negotiated terms (or perhaps under a Creative Commons Licence) while retaining ultimate control of their copyright and some or all of their existing related rights or as yet unknown future rights which they may wish to deploy later.

- **Secondary Publishing Rights**¹ cover a variety of legal mechanisms empowering researchers to retain some of the rights over their publicly funded works rather than assigning them to publishers. The author is normally the beneficiary of the secondary right, with the legislation preventing the alienation of specific usage rights through licensing or assignment to other parties. The right is granted to authors when publishing results from publicly-funded research. Among our case studies, Secondary Publishing Rights legislation is in place in Bulgaria, France, and the Netherlands and now under consideration in Serbia, Slovenia and Ireland. Previously, reform was considered in Italy. Additionally, some mechanisms seek to promote the accessibility of publicly funded research outputs by conferring obligations on agents other than the author, often requiring materials to be made available through a specified repository or repositories under certain conditions (e.g. embargo length or use of specified licences). These obligations often come alongside Secondary Publishing Rights legislation, and indeed Bulgaria adopted obligations into its research legislation in 2024 just after introducing Secondary Publishing Rights in 2023.
- **Legislation on scientific research and innovation** may encourage the open dissemination of research findings or the wide adoption of Open Science practices, influencing institutions to adopt stronger rights retention policies than they might otherwise have done. Such an approach may be adopted due to

¹Lazarova, Ana, Conceptualising the Right to Secondary Publication (May 20, 2024). Caterina Sganga & Tatiana Eleni Synodinou (Eds), *Flexibilities in Copyright Law*, Routledge, Forthcoming, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4934531>

the difficulties of enacting reform to copyright legislation, although the approach will still affect application of copyright law with respect to scholarly outputs. The Open Science Decree adopted in Slovenia in 2023 is the clearest example of such an approach.

- The **national policy environment** driving research can also have an impact, specifically through:
 - **National science policies** often set the agenda for Open Access and research dissemination, defining timelines, and guiding institutions on how to align their own policies and how to support researchers. The National Action Plan for Open Research 2022-2030 in Ireland and the Open Science Roadmap in Finland are good examples of how the national environment is feeding into institutional policy development.
 - Similarly, **national funder policies** offer the main mechanism for incentivising researchers, and can confer urgency and legitimacy on institutions seeking to develop their own policies. The influence of international funders, notably the EU, and alignment of national funders with international collaborative initiatives, notably cOAlition S, also affect how institutional policy development proceeds. The role of funders has been important in shaping policy development and progress in Norway and the UK.
 - **Assessment frameworks** can also have a structuring role, specifically as concerns how they incentivise researchers, what metrics they consider, and how they treat Open Access and different Open Access routes. The consideration of papers on the national research information system has acted as an incentive to researchers in Norway, while the French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS) has adapted its evaluation processes in France as part of its policy.

- **Publishing culture**, namely the dynamics affecting publication venue and choice:
 - **Publishing infrastructure:** Ready access to appropriate publishing platforms, repositories, and journals significantly affects how quickly institutions can adopt – or how easily researchers can comply with – rights retention policies. This was a factor in the speed of development in Norway and the UK and will be a major consideration in Bulgaria’s next steps to reform.
 - **Primary route to Open Access:** The dominant model of achieving Open Access will affect institutional approaches to rights retention – whether this is Green Open Access (self-archiving in repositories), Gold Open Access (paying a fee to be published Open Access in a journal), or through Transformative Agreements (TAs; contracts negotiated with publishers that allow researchers to publish Open Access and transform the underlying business model of the journals covered by the agreement). How Open Access models will affect approaches to rights retention is not predictable. For example, TAs may incentivise institutions to introduce and develop rights retention policies, yet the popularity of TAs with researchers may make engagement with rights retention and the implementation of related policies harder. The strong Green Open Access culture in Ireland is a factor in the adoption approach. Meanwhile, the continued expense of Gold Open Access and lack of progress from TAs are factors in how UK institutions like the N8 take forward rights retention policies.
 - The strength of the culture around **researchers’ freedom to choose where to publish** has affected their willingness to engage with stronger forms of rights retention and, thus, the type of policies being developed. This aspect of research culture has had the most impact in France but is also a factor in Finland.
 - Attitudes to **open licensing** and the willingness of researchers and publishers to adopt more permissive types of licence reflect the prevailing publishing culture and impact the nature of rights retention policies adopted. Bulgaria, Norway and Slovenia provide examples of how open licensing has been or will be implemented without the full adoption or requirement of a CC-BY licence.

Internal factors

The most effective approaches may involve a synergy of efforts at different levels, potentially including national, institutional and funder action. However, all other things being equal, institutional policies have in-built advantages. There is a more permanent and stable relationship between researchers and institutions than other actors. Institutions often directly employ researchers, and there will already be policies and legislation in place that govern the relationship, including labour laws and labour contracts.

The case studies from Norway and the UK specifically focus on institutions which have had policies in place for several years and so provide the best insights on the internal factors affecting policy development:

- **Existing policy stack:** Different institutions have different existing policies in place, and any formalised approach to rights retention will need to consider integration and harmonisation with (at least) existing policies on Open Access or Open Science, intellectual property and copyright, and publishing and dissemination of research.
- **The attitude of leadership:** Institutional leadership can take different stances in relation to rights retention policy. In some cases, a desire to be early adopters or to influence trends on Open Access and Open Science has played an important role; in others, a tendency to be risk-averse has been a factor that leaders within the library or outside institutions have had to address and overcome, often through advocacy and collaborative initiatives.
- **Capacity for support:** An institution's introduction of rights retention policies is often closely linked to its level of support to researchers in understanding the funder requirements placed on them and in negotiation with publishers. This is also a factor that institutions consider when deciding whether to mandate or recommend behaviours to researchers, and one reason why rights retention has developed in parallel with initiatives to increase capacity within libraries or research support services (if separate), as seen in Slovenia and Ireland.
- **Approval processes:** The need to gain approval or seek formal sign-off through committee structures, researcher unions or representation is typically an important step in the process of adoption and has a particular impact on the time it takes to launch and implement policies.

WHAT ARE THE GOALS OF A RIGHTS RETENTION POLICY?

As already highlighted in the definition, the fundamental goal of rights retention policies is to ensure retention of sufficient rights over research outputs to make them immediately openly accessible and reusable in different contexts. As such, while they can exist as stand-alone initiatives, they are also often developed as part of a range of strategies to achieve greater Open Access to research, particularly publicly funded research.

In some cases, policy development begins with a very specifically defined focus or goal within this wider framework. This might be to ensure the accessibility of the long tail of research outputs in subject areas where funding for article processing charges (APCs) or large-scale Open Access agreements are not in place. It might also be to reduce the amount of the overall cost to an institution of making its researchers' outputs openly accessible. It may also encourage researchers not to choose licensing options that transfer reuse rights to the publisher.

Another goal is to achieve greater access to research within a particular country. Institutional policies are often part of a raft of measures that are developed in parallel by stakeholders to reach this end.

Researchers also need to be clear about the requirements of rights retention activities. This can involve bringing together research institutions or other interested stakeholders in the process. This is a pertinent issue. In many jurisdictions, legislation will include copyright laws that grant rights of ownership or use to institutions over the work produced by their researchers. This may be because works created by employees within the scope of their employment are considered 'works made for hire,' meaning an institution holds rights to exploit these works as it employs the researcher. In practice, these rights may not be exercised. Institutions that have exploitation rights sometimes explicitly (or through some implicit means) waive them and intentionally leave researchers to manage them. In other cases, they are not consistent in how they apply them, or there is confusion about whether the legislation applies. Developing and implementing rights retention policies is one way to establish greater clarity and consistency.

Concerning the dividends of rights retention policies, these are early days for the implementation of policies in Europe. Our case studies illustrate, in most countries, that policies are still under development at this stage, and so it is too early to confidently assess what impact rights retention reform will have or to the full extent of the benefits it will bring. Many are still

reviewing the basis on which institutional policies could be established and the extent of the benefits they could bring.

Even in the United Kingdom & Norway, which have been the drivers of interest in and early adopters of institutional rights retention policies since 2022, it is too early to be able to draw definitive conclusions as to impact or response to date, although there are positive signs. In any case, and as already underlined, the most beneficial policy type and level is unavoidably linked to context and how they are formulated.

However, one thing is clear, policy development and implementation help authors and institutions to manage their rights, regardless of other benefits.

WHAT STEPS ARE IMPORTANT WHEN DEVELOPING A POLICY?

For an institution to adopt a rights retention policy, a combination of several strategies is required. There is no single recipe or straightforward sequence of steps to follow; success depends on pursuing multiple strands in combination and adapting to local contexts. None may be essential, and no individual step will be sufficient. Initiatives can focus on collaboration and coordination, lobbying and engaging wide groups of stakeholders, establishing the legal bases for policy development, or training and awareness-raising among researchers.

There is considerable value in making preparations before any formal process is launched to ensure that future policy initiatives have a strong basis for implementation. Such initiatives can come from many different places, most often within libraries or collaborative library groups, but also from legal experts as well as networks or associations of universities.

Our experience suggests that the following elements are most important.

- *Legal advice:* Seek clear legal guidance to understand current options and determine the parameters that will affect how successfully policies can be implemented under existing contract and copyright laws. Legal advice played a key role in policy development in Norway and the UK, and different legal perspectives have played important roles in the Finnish and Italian approaches, as well as driving the nature of reforms in Bulgaria, Slovenia and Serbia.
- *Coalition-building:* Build alliances both within and outside the institution. Internally, engage faculty and researchers across disciplines, institutional leadership, and non-library departments. Facilitate alliances between institutions to accelerate progress and pool resources. Such alliances can also create healthy competition by incentivising institutions to stay ahead of their peers and avoid being

left behind. Externally, collaborate with legal experts, Open Science advocates, civil society organisations, policymakers, and umbrella bodies to strengthen support. The Finnish case study provides a good example of how the library community is working with researchers, rectors and other parties to move forward progress. The case studies of Right2Pub in Italy and SCOIR in Ireland provide good examples of broad stakeholder groups coming together.

- *Copying*: Adapt successful policies from other institutions and fit them to your local context. Review existing reform initiatives, adapt them and tailor them to align with your own institutional needs and context. In our case studies, the Slovenian reform project has learned from and adapted the approach taken in Bulgaria, while the Finnish approach has taken aspects of the work done in the UK & Norway and attempted to adapt them to local circumstances.
- *Engagement*: Emphasise that policies are designed to protect researchers' rights and enhance their agency with respect to publishing contracts. This is especially sensitive and important in contexts where researchers are concerned over threats to their freedom to choose where they publish. The choice over whether a policy is opt-out or opt-in (or indeed leaves such choice to researchers) can be important in addressing potentially diverse needs and reactions. The possibility to opt out has consistently been an important factor in building support for a policy among researchers, even though researchers rarely take advantage of it once the policy is implemented. It is also important to advocate for leadership support.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In summary, institutional policies for rights retention offer a mechanism to safeguard researchers' rights while representing a highly promising route through which institutions are seeking to facilitate Open Access to scholarly outputs. Legislative reform can provide a valuable foundation for institutional policies, but can also take years to achieve. Policy development can allow institutions to take action now and help facilitate greater Open Access to their researchers' work. There is considerable variation in the approaches and policy types emerging, which should encourage others to develop their own initiatives - there is a good chance that there will be a model that works whatever the context.

To those considering how to make progress in their own institution or particular environment, we especially recommend the following:

- Map out the different factors at play in their environment that will affect the extent and nature of policy.
- Do not seek perfection. No such thing exists, and a great deal of progress can be made even in difficult environments and jurisdictions.
- Work with other interested parties, within and outside your institution that can help pool resources and accelerate progress.
- Seek good and creative legal advice. It will help you understand your options and the risks that need to be addressed.

SECTION TWO: OVERVIEW OF THE THEMES AND TRENDS EMERGING FROM CASE STUDIES

This section draws out the key themes emerging from the case studies featured in the report, each with distinct legal and cultural flavours. Rights retention policies are an important tool that can be utilised to accelerate the immediate Open Access publication of research outputs in an institution while acknowledging the importance of keeping rights and the risks of transferring all rights by default.

By exploring the motivations behind rights retention policies, the legislative challenges, and the efforts to raise awareness and engage researchers, diverse institutions and national environments are charting their own paths, albeit with comparable challenges and related solutions.

PROGRESS TO DATE

Interest in this type of policy increased rapidly in 2022 when cOAlition S proposed it as a possible route to Open Access, and consideration of how to develop policies is now underway in many European countries. Nonetheless, these are early days for the implementation of rights retention policies in Europe. This is the case for each of the case studies featured, even in Norway and the UK, which have more established policies.

Despite the early stage, the motivation of institutions for exploring rights retention policies are clear. They seek greater Open Access to research outputs and publications, often as a part of a raft of measures. Institutional policies seek to clarify what rights researchers have and how they are implemented in practice; they seek to improve accessibility to all published research outputs whilst making Open Access more affordable.

It is also clear that there is a focus on developing the national policy environment and legislation alongside awareness-raising initiatives. We are also seeing that various forms of institutional policy are appropriate in different contexts. Policies may be standalone or incorporated into existing policy stacks. They may mandate specific behaviours or simply recommend them and offer support. Coverage varies, and there are differences in how open licensing is required or recommended.

LEGISLATIVE AND NON-LEGISLATIVE COMPONENTS

A range of factors can impact the best approach to take – most notably legislation, as the interplay between institutional policies and national law can be complex and needs to be carefully managed. Among our case studies, we see a number of different approaches to combining legislation and non-legislative approaches:

- Two case studies – in Finland and Italy – about initiatives that focus on bringing institutions together and providing education and training since it appears impossible to achieve legislative reform within a reasonable time frame.
- Two case studies – France and the Netherlands – in countries where legislative reform has already introduced Secondary Publishing Rights. Initiatives in these countries are focused on institutional dialogue and awareness-raising, and seeking a coherent institutional policy response to ensure that the full benefits can be realised.
- Two case studies – in Ireland and Slovenia – about initiatives taking holistic approaches at the national level, exploring legislative reform in parallel to institutional policy adoption.
- One case study – in Bulgaria – where there is a need to make progress at the institutional level to ensure that recent legislative reforms have their desired effect.
- One case study – in Serbia – in which legislative reform is being explored in the hope that it can help build something concrete based on long-standing discussion about and interest in rights retention.

There is no one-size-fits-all approach to institutional rights retention vis-à-vis law, or a single correct way to develop and implement an institutional policy.

Approaches must be tailored to the specific contexts and legal environments, and as we hope the case studies demonstrate, agents across the research landscape can make significant contributions.

SECONDARY PUBLISHING RIGHTS

As highlighted above, Secondary Publishing Rights legislation already exists in three of the countries covered by our case studies (Bulgaria, France and the Netherlands), is being actively considered in three more (Ireland, Slovenia and Serbia), and has previously been considered in Italy.

Secondary Publishing Rights legislation is most settled in France and the Netherlands. In the Netherlands, the Taverne Amendment has led to

coordinated efforts by universities to support implementation, but has not fully resolved confusion and complexity in how researchers' rights are retained and exercised in practice. In response, additional work is being pursued by the Universities of the Netherlands. In France, the introduction of Secondary Publishing Rights has set the baseline for non-mandatory rights retention policies adopted by research institutions. However, attempts to move beyond this and mandate specific behaviour by researchers or to encourage them to retain greater rights have not yet been successful due to the need to advance culture change.

Bulgaria, Slovenia and Ireland offer differing examples of how Secondary Publishing Rights reform is being pursued as part of a broader strategy that also includes the introduction of rights retention policies at an institutional level. The approach may be sequential, with Secondary Publishing Rights leading to a programme encouraging and pushing institutions to bring in policies addressing rights retention, e.g. in Bulgaria. Alternatively, Secondary Publishing Rights may be pursued in parallel to institutional dialogue, as strands of a larger overarching project – Ireland is the primary example of this, although even here, there is a prioritisation of different elements over time.

We consistently see that copyright reform is hard and inevitably involves a wider range of interest groups, notably the broader publishing industry outside academic and scholarly publishing. As such, the introduction of Secondary Publishing Rights is sometimes pursued outside of copyright legislation, although it does affect the application of copyright law with respect to scholarly outputs. In Slovenia, for example, Secondary Publishing Rights will be implemented via a Scientific Research and Innovation Activities Act and an Open Science Decree.

There has not yet been any significant move to introduce Secondary Publishing Rights when there is an existing viable route to pursue rights retention – such as the UK – or where the institutional leadership has been willing to push for policy adoption without such a clear legal route or any realistic possibility of legal reform -- notably in Norway and Finland.

Approaches toward rights retention have been adapted to accommodate the status of Secondary Publishing Rights, but not all in straightforward ways. A range of other factors also come into play, as illustrated by our case studies.

THE WIDER ENVIRONMENT

The willingness and capacity of leadership to support reform are critical, along with existing policies and the mechanisms through which policies are approved. Coalition-building and collaboration are hallmarks of the initiatives that have made the greatest progress.

In particular, engagement with researchers on the terms most likely to appeal to them remains a crucial (if underrated) factor. Above all, emphasising that the goal of reform is to protect – not restrict – freedoms is key. In France, Nantes Université faced a court challenge from one of their researchers who argued that the University's policy infringed the freedom of academics to choose where to publish by mandating specific behaviours. The University withdrew the policy before the case went to court.

Lots of work has been put into engaging researchers across the countries covered in the different case studies and so avoid such situations, with Italy providing a very clear example of an approach based on feedback and engagement with researchers.

Acceptance is possible. In countries where policies are already common, negative researcher reaction has been limited. In both Norway and the UK, researcher engagement with policy launches ranges from indifference to enthusiasm. York University in the UK and University of Tromsø – The Arctic University of Norway (UiT) have both seen measurable increases in materials being made openly accessible since they formally adopted rights retention policies. UiT is particularly notable, as it has now achieved >96% of articles published by its faculty being made openly accessible in accordance with its Open Access policy. Rights retention has been the key tool at UiT's disposal in supporting the long tail of researchers who publish in areas not covered by other arrangements.

Meanwhile, stated negative publisher reactions to rights retention policy development have not translated into decisive action. The publishing community has not reacted strongly to the most advanced policy environments, specifically in the UK and Norway. This may change in the UK in 2025 if, like the University of York (a part of the N8 Research Partnership of research-intensive institutions in the North of England featured in our case study), more institutions choose to exit from Transformative Agreements.

CONCLUSION

Taken together, the case studies demonstrate the variety of available paths to adopting rights retention policies. While legal reforms – in particular the introduction of Secondary Publishing Rights – provide a valuable legal backstop and impetus for change, progress on the ground also relies on clear institutional policies to ensure rights are understood and utilised. Unavoidably, legislative reform also takes time, and faster progress can often be achieved through institutional policy development where leadership and collaboration enable it.

The examples from Norway and the UK illustrate how a rights retention policy can yield high levels of Open Access, and other examples show the benefits of adapting strategies to legislative reform depending on the context in different countries. Ultimately, there is no universal blueprint, but the experiences detailed here show the phase of rapid progress that started in 2022 and 2023 continues in a broad range of contexts, continuing to facilitate Open Access to research.

SECTION THREE: DETAILED CASE STUDIES

BULGARIA

A network of non-governmental organisations and librarian groups has taken a structured approach to seeking reform through legislation and institutional policy change. The initial reform was driven by Members of Parliament with backgrounds in research, Open Science, and civil society, and has involved a pioneering staged introduction of Secondary Publishing Rights and Obligations. Focus has now moved to developing institutional rights retention policies and accompanying support mechanisms for researchers; such policies are essential to ensure that the legislative reform can have its desired effects.

Introduction of legislation on Secondary Publishing

Bulgaria is the first country to have both a Secondary Publication Right and a Secondary Publication Obligation incorporated in laws at the national level.² This has happened even though the main national research funding organisation, National Science Fund of Bulgaria (BNSF) is still considering how or whether to implement Open Access requirements in its project grants. Prior to the legislative developments, there were no known rights retention policies within Bulgarian research performing and higher education institutions.

Progress in legislative changes has been supported by a network of non-governmental organisations and librarian groups. Those different groups and organisations have been able to influence policy makers and politicians to support legal reform.

Secondary Publishing Rights first

Secondary Publishing Rights were introduced in late 2023, through amendments to the [Copyright and Neighbouring Rights Act \(CNRA\)](#). The reform of this Act was undertaken to implement the EU [Directive on Copyright in the Digital Single Market](#). It took three years to achieve agreement of the copyright reform, over which time awareness of the potential benefits of Secondary Publishing Rights grew. The revision of the Copyright Act was undertaken to better protect rights, and improve authors' ability to negotiate with those who seek exclusive transfer of copyright.

² Lazarova, Ana, Conceptualising the Right to Secondary Publication (May 20, 2024). Caterina Sganga & Tatiana Eleni Synodinou (Eds), *Flexibilities in Copyright Law*, Routledge, Forthcoming, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4934531>

Support for reform arose from a combination of interest, influence and expertise within Members of Parliament who had a background in research, Open Science and civil society. Stakeholder consultations brought support from research and higher education institutions who advocated around the specifics of the proposed Secondary Publishing Rights regime. Engagement efforts by supporters of the reform focused on raising awareness that OA did not need to be costly and achieved only through payment of APCs.

As a result of this effort, a text creating a Secondary Publishing Right was included in the act as article 60 (paragraph 2 et seq.):

“[t]he author of a work of academic literature created on the occasion of a research, funded in whole or in part by public funding, shall retain the right to make that work or parts thereof available in not-for-profit educational or scientific repositories after its acceptance for publication by a publisher, and shall be obliged to mention the publisher when doing so.”

The Secondary Publishing Right amendment permits re-publication of publicly funded academic works without an embargo. Public funding is here understood as any type of public financial support, both in form of employment or the receipt of project grant funding (national or international). Importantly, the Secondary Publishing Right as it is formulated in the following paragraphs of this article secures authors from contractual override:

“[a]ny arrangement which prevents or restricts what is provided for in para 2 shall be null and void.” (paragraph 3)

and

‘a publisher may not impose restrictions on the publication of a work of academic literature solely on the grounds that it has already been published in a not-for-profit educational or scientific repository.’ (paragraph 4)

However, this Secondary Publishing Rights clause does not specify the use of any particular licence as there was insufficient support for such a provision, and it was considered to be unduly interfering in the author-publisher relationship.

Secondary Publication Obligation next

Including a Secondary Publishing Right in Bulgarian copyright law was a great achievement, but it was just one piece of a puzzle. It gave authors a right that they could exercise, but there was no obligation for them or for their employing institutions actually to implement it in practice, and so to achieve Open Access goals. Addressing this was a necessary next step.

A Secondary Publication Obligation was therefore introduced in May 2024 through the introduction of a [Law on the Promotion of Scholarly Research and Innovation](#). This law contains a chapter on the promotion of Open Science, which covers research funding and dissemination of results. Under the law, according to Article 80 (paragraph 2):

“Authors of publications resulting from publicly funded research shall make available for publication a digital copy of the publication or a version thereof in the repository referred to in Article 78(2).”

The [Bulgarian Open Science Portal](#) was appointed as a central repository and access point.

Internal working groups including librarians and academics worked on the provisions in the law, but there were diverse perspectives and significant debate within the Ministry of Education and Science and with other stakeholders. As a result, the text does not refer to ‘reuse’ explicitly and wording around Open Access and other related provisions is not as precise as it might otherwise have been.

Implementation requires further work - and policies

The groups working together to advance legislative reform in Bulgaria have been clear that they see Secondary Publication Obligations and Secondary Publishing Rights as necessary complements to each other - neither on its own is fully effective as a means of ensuring authors (and their institutions) can retain their rights and then publish openly. One without the other risks placing the burdens on the weakest parties in terms of bargaining power, by pressuring researchers to ignore contractual obligations without empowering them to do so. The other creates the possibility of open access publishing, but not the impetus to realise it.

The introduction of Secondary Publishing Rights or Secondary Publication Obligations without complementary policy and regulation to support implementation is likely to be insufficient to achieve relevant Open Science goals fully. This will be pursued in Bulgaria through additional ordinances issued by relevant authorities such as the Council of Ministers or the Ministry of Education and Science. These ordinances will provide the necessary regulatory framework, timelines and mechanisms to implement and enforce the legislative reform. They are under development and will go ahead after a delay caused by changes in parliament and in government. There is currently a public consultation on a proposal for an ordinance for the secondary publication of publicly funded research which ends in January 2025.

There also is a need to foster a broader embrace of open science values within the Bulgarian academic community, and this will be the focus of supporters of legislative reform and non-legislative measures in the next phase of implementation. There will need to be adequate funder and institutional rights retention policies as well as support mechanisms for researchers - at present institutional documents generally encourage Open Science and incentivise Open Access, but do not mention rights retention. Technical issues will also have to be addressed to ensure that institutional repositories and the national portal are sufficiently interoperable to ensure researchers and their institutions can both exercise their rights and comply with their legal requirements.

FINLAND

The Finnish University Libraries Network (FUN) has sought to learn from experiences in the UK, Norway and other Scandinavian countries. There is little appetite for legislative reform, and no clear existing legal basis for institutional rights retention policies. As such, their approach has been to build support across a network of institutions, from rectors and other stakeholders, with many research organisations prepared to move together and planning to adopt institutional rights retention policies together before the end of 2025.

Progress over many years

There is strong support for Open Science in Finland, and much progress has been made on Open Access. The country is currently working on a new [Roadmap for Open Science](#), which places an emphasis on the importance of access to research to ensure economic stability in Finland, as well as covering open publishing, open research data and infrastructure, open education and open scholarship.

The Finnish University Libraries Network (FUN) co-ordinates and develops cooperation among university libraries on a national level. Over many years, it has actively promoted Open Access and Open Science through national initiatives and international collaboration.

It recently set up a working group, chaired by the Chief Specialist of Open Science at Tampere University, seeking to establish a feasible approach to rights retention in Finland. The group has been meeting and working on the task through most of 2024, but it has proven as a complex challenge. In almost all areas, many factors also need to be considered and resolved to establish and promote rights retention policies at the institutional level.

Blockers to progress

There remains confusion and uncertainty in some quarters. Concerns about academic freedom and the ability of researchers to publish where they wish under Open Access mandates remain, including among the Research Council of Finland and Professoriliitto, the Finnish Union of University Professors. The [Finnish Association for Scholarly Publishing](#) remains generally unsupportive of Open Science and Open Access since there is perceived to be a lack of sustainable models in place to transition Finnish language journals to Open Access in the current publishing environment.

There is also only partial support in institutions for the adoption of rights retention policies. This stems in part from scepticism and aversion to being the first mover among the leadership of some institutions. There is also a fear that if researchers were to actively oppose rights retention policies it could lead to a broader opposition to Open Access and Open Science, undermining broader efforts to reform. There is also no appetite among institutions for change to the current status quo in employment contracts

to assert or assign some form of copyright ownership to employing institutions.

In Finland, researchers own the copyright to their written work rather than their employing institutions. There is no obvious basis in copyright or contract law that would allow secondary publishing or rights retention without legislative reform of some kind. Such reform is unpopular with research unions and would be unlikely to find support among university leadership.

Finding the right Finnish approach

FUN is now working towards an approach that echoes that of institutions in Norway or the UK. There, the adoption of institutional rights retention policies was accompanied by institutional leadership formally stepping in to take responsibility and assert a right to make articles written by their researchers available. Such an approach is described by FUN as 'parallel publishing', with materials available immediately via repositories under CC licences. Crucially, FUN's proposals would also ensure all researchers could opt out of this 'parallel publishing', thus helping to address some of the concerns expressed.

The working group took proposals to the whole group of FUN library directors in late 2024 for review and approval. FUN accepted the proposal, written by the working group, in December 2024. Now the ambition is to submit a formal proposal in the first half of 2025 to the Council of Rectors of Finnish Universities (Unifi) in the hope that institutional rights retention policies could be in place by the end of the year.

A staged engagement and communications campaign will also now begin to bring the plans to broader stakeholders, most significantly to gain the support of University Rectors.

The campaign will be undertaken by individual librarians in their institutions as part of a wider campaign for support, emphasising the international development of rights retention and the value of ensuring all research papers are accessible rather than just those covered by Read and Publish Agreements. It would emphasise the importance of a proposed simultaneous launch by all Finnish universities, underpinned by librarian training to provide the necessary support to researchers, with the ambition that all research institutions will follow.

FRANCE

Secondary Publishing Rights are already established in French law, and institutional policies have been adopted with recommendations around rights retention. This has led to a tangible increase in materials being made openly accessible. However, there has not been widespread adoption of policies which mandate the retention of rights by authors or mandate that they adopt specific behaviours. Attempts to bring in policies of this type have proved controversial. As such, further reform efforts are focused on training and awareness-raising - seeking to ensure researchers and librarians understand that rights retention will not infringe academics' freedom to choose where they publish.

Culture of Academic Freedom

French research culture strongly values academic freedom. Respecting authors and their choices is fundamental, and this plays out in discussions about the freedom of authors to choose where to publish their research.

The commitment to this academic freedom underpins copyright as applied to written research outputs. For French public sector employees, copyright in written work automatically transfers to their employer. However, the law explicitly exempts researchers, even if employed by a public institution, who are using public funding or working in a public laboratory with public equipment. The copyright owner of research outputs is always the individual author.

Researchers and the French publishing industry strongly support this approach to copyright. While support for Open Science is strong in France, some stakeholders have expressed concerns that Open Science reforms might affect copyright.

Understanding this culture is key to understanding how rights retention has evolved in the country. In 2016, France implemented a Secondary Publishing Right into its [copyright law](#). The Secondary Publishing Right provision was subject to considerable debate in the research sector and parliament before its adoption, based on concerns that it may harm the interests of certain private publishers. Ultimately, the provision was adopted because it enhanced the rights of authors and did not affect their freedoms.

Now adopted, it ensures the Version of Record for journal articles can be made available after a maximum embargo period of 6 months for science, technology and medicine and 12 months for the humanities and social science. It applies where research is at least 50% publicly funded. The law does not require immediate deposit nor the use of any specific open licence.

Implications for policies

The introduction of a Secondary Publishing Right has provided the context for rights retention policy development in institutions.

Most leading research institutions in France and many universities have implemented non-mandatory policies that strongly encourage researchers

to retain their rights and support them in fulfilling their obligations to funders. The largest funding agency in France is the Agence Nationale de la Recherche (National Research Agency; ANR). ANR is a member of cOAlition S and supports its rights retention strategy. ANR requires funded researchers to follow this strategy and ensure all articles arising from their research are made immediately Open Access.

In general, French research institutions have not attempted to implement policies mandating specific behaviour by researchers. The highest profile institution to make such an attempt, Nantes Université, has faced a court challenge from one of their researchers who argued that the policy infringed their academic freedom. The University withdrew the policy before the case could proceed to court.

The Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (French National Centre for Scientific Research; CNRS) has been able to go further as it has adapted its evaluation processes around rights retention. CNRS is a government-funded agency that conducts research in all scientific fields and the largest employer of researchers in France. It also conducts the evaluation of individual researchers. For a publication to count toward their evaluation, researchers must ensure it is deposited into the national open archive (HAL). Researchers can choose whether to upload their publications or not, but their decision will affect their evaluation. Researchers have the right to do this because of the Secondary Publishing Right provision in French law, which protects their rights. CNRS's policy does not affect any of the rights researchers have as a result of French copyright rules.

CNRS is in a specific position as it evaluates individual researchers, and so can adopt a policy of this type. The High Council for the Evaluation of Research (HCERES) is another national agency with such an opportunity. HCERES evaluates higher education and research institutions, and specifically laboratories. It strongly encourages laboratories to use HAL, and every time a laboratory has a scheduled evaluation, HAL sets up a simple system for generating laboratory bibliographies which then feed into the reports to be submitted to the HCERES.

Opportunities for further work

The [French KR21 initiative](#), launched in 2024, aims to increase awareness and encourage institutional staff to actively support researchers. Given the French context, the initiative has focused on raising awareness of rights retention in general and the rights bestowed by the copyright framework in particular. A training programme has been launched for academic staff, librarians, and administrative personnel who support researchers. It aims to help institutions develop stronger policies to support and assist researchers during publisher negotiations.

IRELAND

The 'Secondary Rights, Copyright, Open Access, Institutional Policies, and Rights Retention' initiative (SCOIR) in Ireland has been funded by Ireland's National Open Research Forum (NORF) with engagement from KR21. SCOIR is pursuing legislative reform to allow researchers to deposit manuscripts in parallel with the development of institutional policies that support rights retention. This twin-track approach has been made possible due to the range of expertise at the initiative's disposal through its expert advisory panel and own leadership. It comes at a fortuitous time as many institutions are seeking to renew or review their Open Access policies or, in the case of several of the Technological Universities, to introduce them for the first time.

What is SCOIR?

The [SCOIR initiative](#) aims to achieve 100% Open Access to publicly funded research through policy and legislative changes. Professor Eoin O'Dell from the School of Law at Trinity College Dublin and Frances Madden, the Assistant Head of Library Services: Research Services from TU Dublin lead the project.

SCOIR is funded by Ireland's [National Open Research Forum](#) (NORF). NORF was established in 2017 to drive the Irish agenda for open research. It is a Government of Ireland initiative, funded by the Department of Further and Higher Education, Research, Innovation and Science, through the Higher Education Authority and supported by the Royal Irish Academy and the [Digital Repository of Ireland](#).

The activities of NORF are overseen by the National Open Research Coordinator. NORF develops national objectives and coordinated actions to support Ireland's transition to Open Research, aligned with international developments, most recently through the [National Action Plan for Open Research 2022-2030](#). Since 2022, NORF has administered the Open Research Fund to deliver priority actions in the National Action Plan for Open Research and foster uptake of Open Research in Ireland. Another NORF-funded project, [PublishOpen Access](#), seeks to establish a Diamond Open Access publishing platform for Ireland and has direct relevance and interaction with SCOIR. Other NORF projects relevant to SCOIR are the [National Open Access Monitor](#) and the [Open Access Repository Assessment and Alignment](#) project.

SCOIR stands for 'Secondary Rights, Copyright, Open Access, Institutional Policies, and Rights Retention', highlighting the holistic approach the initiative seeks to reform and achieve progress on Open Access. 'Scoil' is also the Irish word for "unharness," a deliberate 'backronym' reflecting the partnership's desire to 'unharness' the power of Open Research.

It is a good time to seek to engage the institutional community in policy reform. Many Irish institutions have Open Access policies that have not been reviewed for a number of years. Historically, there has been a strong repository and Green Open Access culture in Ireland but evidence at the institutional level appears to show that this has been diminished by the widespread recent adoption of Read and Publish deals, the parallel tightening of publisher restrictions (such as prohibitively lengthy embargos) on the self-archiving of Accepted Manuscripts, and other factors. Regarding transformative agreements, the National Action Plan for Open Research states that “While transformative agreements play a role in accelerating open access options with a range of publishers, such agreements should be considered transitional and form part of a broader strategy that encompasses and promotes a diversity of open access publishing models and options.”

Also, the establishment and reform of Ireland’s Technological Universities (TUs) over the last 5-10 years has included an ambition to grow their research intensity. The TUs have sought ways to do this built on strong Open Access commitments and repository cultures, as seen in the development of [TU-Net](#), the [OpenAIRE](#)-developed online network for the Irish Technological Universities to share expertise, information and resources via open access publications, data, software and other research outputs.

Parallel approaches

There are two key strands - one focused on developing and drafting appropriate legislation, and one on creating model frameworks for institutional and funder policies. The initial proposal was drafted in response to a call for expressions of interest for projects aimed at “developing, strengthening and implementing institutional policies for Open Access and rights retention to drive and Open Access uptake.

The initial call from the funder for expressions of interest did not include the legislative element (which was being viewed separately at the time). However, the legal expertise of the team, particularly that of Professor Eoin O’Dell (chair of Ireland’s Copyright Review Committee), its postgraduate law students, and its international advisory panel, presented the opportunity to bring the legal and policy elements together in a single project. SCOIR has benefited significantly from the engagement of KR21.

The project has developed these strands in parallel, with sequential elements that will emerge later in the project’s second year. Supporting these strands, SCOIR has a work package focused on the alignment of its legal and policy strands, advocacy and communication, management of the proposed reforms, and creation of instructional and support resources.

The approach to legislation

The legislative strand is rooted in the complexities of Ireland's Copyright Act 2000 and a recognition that any attempt to reform the Act would be highly unlikely to succeed in the timeframe available to SCOIR. The Copyright Act 2000 states that initial copyright is owned by the author or owner of the work except in cases where the work is undertaken in the course of the conduct of employment, in which case it belongs to the employer.

In practice, the Intellectual Property policies of almost all Irish research-performing institutions acknowledge the Act, with the exception of outputs where the institution explicitly waives its right in favour of the author. Authors then often hand exclusive rights over to publishers.

SCOIR has developed a Research Outputs and Open Access Bill, which would allow authors to deposit manuscripts in a repository without interfering with Copyright Act provisions. The Research Outputs and Open Access Bill will enable authors to deposit an Author Accepted Manuscript (AAM) in a repository immediately on acceptance and recommends using a CC-BY licence but accepts other CC licences. The Bill applies to any researchers who are wholly or in part 'publicly funded', which is defined expansively to include (say) salaries and contracts.

The Bill requires institutions to support researchers by providing the environment, workflows, infrastructures and support to enable them to exercise these rights. If monitoring and reporting reveal that the Bill's provisions are not functioning effectively, it is anticipated that appeals can be made to the existing Ombudsman which deals with complaints against providers of public services including government departments, local authorities and publicly funded third-level education bodies.

The draft Bill was published in late 2024 and underwent a limited consultation before a more comprehensive campaign commenced engaging a wide range of parties, including special interest groups, the Irish Copyright Licensing Agency, bodies representing specific research disciplines, the Irish University Association, and related NORF-funded projects.

In 2025, the Bill will enter a new phase of consultation and review, the outcome of which will be taken to the government and legislators to seek support. It is anticipated that it will take up to two years before the Bill could be signed into law, and a great deal of consideration has gone into hearing and anticipating possible objections.

The approach to institutional policy

A parallel strand is focused on policies for institutions and funders. It is aimed at developing a flexible model policy. The key aim is to align institutional and university policies with the [National Framework on the Transition to an Open Research Environment](#) adopted by NORF in July 2019 and with the National Action Plan for Open Research.

The model policy commits institutions to adopt workflows that respect author IP and autonomy, to support freedom of researchers to publish wherever deemed appropriate, and to facilitate their ability to exercise their rights in line with SCOIR's proposed legislative reform.

The language of the policy is being developed to align with the draft Bill but to work independently if there is a delay in the Bill's enactment. The policy requires the institution to put workflows in place to make publications Open Access, with Creative Commons licences, through the institutional repository, and for the institution's employees to deposit an appropriate version of the publication in the repository. The policy makes no reference to rights retention, but as the institution's employees are required to deposit publications in the repository and those publications are made available with CC licences, this means that those employees retain the rights to the AAM of their publications.

The policy requires the university's employees to deposit an appropriate version of the publication in the repository. Where the publication has been made open access via the publisher, the version of record is deposited (in which the author will already have retained copyright). Otherwise, the author's accepted manuscript is the version that is required to be deposited as this does not infringe the publisher's copyright. The policy also requires the university to put workflows in place to make publications (accompanied by Creative Commons licenses) open access through the institutional repository. These workflows enable the deposit requirement for university employees. In complying with the deposit requirement, employees retain their rights to the author's accepted manuscript of their publication.

The first draft policies were made available for consultation on the SCOIR website in autumn 2024. Webinars and other advocacy activities are scheduled to raise awareness and encourage feedback. Endorsing SCOIR's sequential approach, the consultation has highlighted that institutions cannot simply be told to adopt rights retention. This must come as a reaction to provisions in the legislation and the need to support researchers. If enacted, the Research Outputs and Open Access Act will mark a significant milestone towards the national aim "to implement a sustainable and inclusive course of achieving 100% Open Access to research publications by 2030".

The leadership of SCOIR brings awareness of issues, deep expertise and relevant networks to enable them to build on these foundations. Their approach is structured, multilayered, and fundamentally built on the socialisation of their ideas and the ambition to make the case to the community. The following two years will determine what route the reforms take.

ITALY

Right2Pub was a time-limited Italian initiative that was launched in late 2023. It aimed to strengthen awareness of and action for researchers' rights to publish and the reuse of their own work. Right2Pub brought together the Institute of Legal Informatics and Judicial Systems (IGSG), libraries within the National Research Council (CNR), and Creative Commons Italy. Right2Pub followed three phases: researching the scientific community's awareness of rights and copyright, developing targeted training and resources, and advocating for legislative reform. Right2Pub's work is now being carried forward by various routes that continue to expand training, call for legal reform, and encourage institutional mandates that support authors' rights retention.

Right2Pub

[Right2Pub](#) - Balancing Publication Rights is an initiative launched in late 2023 in Italy, through the Knowledge Rights 21 programme, to undertake research and raise awareness of the need to maintain and expand the authors' rights of Italian researchers. Right2Pub brings together representatives from a broad spectrum of organisations in Italy who are interested in these topics.

The initiative is supported by KR21 and led by the [Institute of Legal Informatics and Judicial Systems](#) (Istituto di Informatica Giuridica e Sistemi Giudiziari; IGSG), which focuses on the intersection between law and information technologies and the right to access information. They also represent libraries from within [Italy's National Research Council](#) (Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche or CNR), i.e. the "Dario Nobili" Library of the CNR Territorial Research Area of Bologna & the Library and Scientific Documentation Centre of the CNR Research Area of Pisa which have a focus on supporting researchers and promoting the benefits of Open Science. Creative Commons Italy is also represented and active in Right2Pub.

All the research activities carried out at Right2Pub are directed toward building evidence around needs for institutional policy reform in Italy. The project has reviewed international approaches such as those in the USA, UK and Norway, but established that there was insufficient institutional readiness to copy or adapt these in Italy, and no legislative basis. Rights retention is a very new topic at the institutional level.

Nonetheless, CNR has adopted a [roadmap for Open Science](#), which includes a commitment to rights retention. Still, there has yet to be a concerted effort to implement it. CNR has not joined cOAlition S, and most institutional Open Access policies, including those of CNR, are not mandatory and do not adopt formal rights retention language. However, there is a wide range of levels of compliance with these rights retention provisions, with some institutions seeing broad support for Open Access among researchers despite non-compulsory policies.

A three-phase approach

The Right2Pub approach has undertaken three distinct phases as it seeks to expand researcher rights. The first was a research phase that sought to gain a deeper understanding of perceptions and awareness of rights among researchers and the institutional staff that support them. This was undertaken through a mixture of surveys and focus groups. The results demonstrated a worryingly low awareness among researchers of all relevant topics: copyright, open licensing, their rights and how to use them.

Support staff in institutional libraries had a greater level of knowledge about these topics but still needed to learn more about the licensing of scientific results and the nature of Creative Commons (CC) licences. This group also expressed frustration about researchers' lack of engagement and interest.

One clear divide in attitudes emerged. Researchers focused on being accepted by their journal of choice, irrespective of the impact on their rights to reuse or copyright ownership. Support staff, however, prioritised making sure that materials were made available through institutional repositories.

This led naturally to a second phase of development of resources and information, which was spread through training and a dedicated website. Right2Pub developed full-day training sessions for researchers and support staff, mainly librarians. These consisted of:

- presentations by experts on relevant topics, for example, on Italian copyright law and CC licences;
- discussion and Q&A on reform of processes and ensuring compliance with legislation and funder requirements;
- a session focused on Open Access and how to retain rights through negotiation with publishers, as well as ensuring papers were placed within an institutional repository.

The training was trialled twice in Pisa and Bologna for an audience of researchers, librarians and other support staff from across the two cities and broader regions. The training succeeded in engaging researchers by focusing on their rights, including their current rights, the importance of those rights, and what happens when they publish and give away rights to the publisher. This proved to be a very good way to talk to researchers and expose them to a different perspective.

Legislative change

The third phase was to advocate for change in law and practice in Italy toward a Secondary Publishing Right. Work here drew on findings from the first phase and ran in parallel to the second phase, but also drew on the experience of attempts to reform Italian copyright law in 2018 that ultimately failed due to changes in government and lack of support.

Initial copyright ownership in Italy varies. Specifically, if a work is 'commissioned' then the rights are held by the university or research organisation. Researchers hold ownership under other circumstances, but authors frequently sign away rights to publishers without knowing or confirming whether they have the authority to do so. Italian law grants authors the rights to republish journal articles for non-commercial purposes in a repository after an 18-month embargo or 24 months in the humanities and social sciences. Crucially, however, this provision applies 'salvo patto contrario' - unless otherwise signed away. In other words, the secondary publishing right it confers is lost if a researcher grants a publisher exclusive rights under a publishing agreement.

Right2Pub organised [two conferences](#) in late 2023 and 2024 to discuss legislative reform and various approaches. One route considered was the removal of the three words 'salvo patto contrario' from the relevant clause. This would have quickly strengthened researchers' secondary publishing rights. However, this would apply to an extensive range of works rather than simply journal articles, risking creating significant unintended consequences and opposition to reform.

A second option proposes a new piece of legislation to revise Art 42 of the Italian Copyright Law, drawing on recent reforms adopted in Bulgaria. This grants authors in receipt of any public funding the right to reuse their own works and republish them in an educational (i.e. non-commercial) repository with no embargo period. The reform proposed would refer in general to scientific works not limiting to those who had published in journals, nor excluding monographs or other research outputs. It would also remain neutral on the type of licence researchers could / should use. These different components have been chosen to increase the chances of legislative change being adopted.

Future

Right2Pub was conceived as a time-limited project, although it is looking to ensure that its work has an ongoing impact and can be continued through the work of other parties.

The training developed will continue. It has already been tailored to be delivered in other contexts, such as smaller research institutions, specific disciplines and hybrid settings. It continues to be offered to the wider network of CNR organisations and libraries, both in person and hybrid.

The IGSG/CNR working group, the [Copyright Law and Access to Knowledge Policies Group](#) (CLAKP) created on the occasion of the Right2Pub project to support the activity of KR21 National Coordinator, will continue work on these topics with events, training and advocacy.

The members of Right2Pub intend to launch an active advocacy campaign in conjunction with the publication of a [guide](#) to support authors and launched a book [manifesto](#) in autumn 2024 that supports Italian researchers to understand copyright and secondary publishing rights and

rights retention under Italian law. Work going forward will involve reconnecting all stakeholders already engaged in the process and seeking consensus among political parties about the need for a path to legislative reform.

Finally, there is additionally hope of raising awareness of copyright reform and rights retention among the scientific community beyond CNR, and to accelerate the development of an institutional policy within CNR that mandates Open Access and actively promotes rights retention to the extent currently permitted by Italian legislation.

NETHERLANDS

The Taverne Amendment (2015) grants researchers a Secondary Publishing Right for short scientific works. This has been actively implemented since 2019 by a coalition of universities encouraging researchers to take advantage of their rights. However, variations in copyright ownership and rights retention practice persist because of different interpretations and ways of working in different institutions, and funder requirements which go beyond what the Taverne Amendment anticipated. Working groups of The Universities of the Netherlands are seeking to resolve this through a combination of dialogue, coordinated action and providing clarity over the differences between institutions.

Many legal interpretations

The [Copyright Act in the Netherlands \(Aw\)](#) regulates who owns copyright in a work created by an employee in the service of their employer. According to Article 7 of the Act, the employer can be the copyright holder, provided that (cumulative) conditions are met:

1. there is an employment relationship;
2. the work was created in connection with the performance of that employment;
3. there is 'determinability' from the employer, that is, the employer must have some level of control or influence over the creation of the work

The third condition has sparked discussion over many decades as to whether the determinability requirement in the Copyright Act can be met in the case of scientific works created in the service of a university.

Under Article 7, the employer has the right to make other agreements with the employees that place the copyrights in the hands of the individual employee. Many universities have done this or do this in practice.

Many interpretations exist of condition 3. For some, this means copyright resides with the research institution as employer, whereas the author retains ownership for others. This strongly depends on the kind of scholarly output: the largest differences between universities regard how articles are treated, while there is more alignment on software and educational output.

Attempts to harmonise interpretations towards a national policy go back many decades. In 2015, an attempt to establish a settled position that assigned the rights to the employer proved untenable due to opposition from researchers. In practice, academics routinely sign agreements with publishers without considering whether they have the right to do so.

Additionally, the [Taverne Amendment](#) (Article 25fa) to the national copyright framework came into effect in 2015. It confers a Secondary Publishing Right onto authors, enabling researchers whose short academic work has been supported by public funds to make their outputs publicly

available after a reasonable period, thus permitting them to put a book chapter or journal article into a repository.

However, more recently, it has become apparent that rights granted to researchers by Taverne are insufficient for them to adhere to the requirements of the [Dutch Research Council](#) (NWO, Dutch: Nederlandse Organisatie voor Wetenschappelijk Onderzoek). As signatories of Plan S, NWO requires researchers to publish in Open Access journals or immediately make a copy of their research available through a repository. NWO also requires a CC-BY licence, while Taverne is silent on the issue of licence choice.

Policy response from institutions

Dutch universities have co-ordinated their actions in this space. The “You share, we take care!” pilot initiative was adopted in the light of Taverne in 2019. All the major institutions signed a pledge to ensure that researchers were encouraged to take advantage of the amendment, and institutions pledged that in the event of legal action from publishers, they would bear any legal costs collectively. Taverne was thus effectively implemented by knowledge institutions, and the ‘reasonable period’ was set to six months as tested during the pilot. After successful evaluation of the pilot in 2020, the approach has been scaled up to include all institutions on an opt-in basis.

In 2022-2023 a working group of the [Universities of the Netherlands](#) (Universiteiten van Nederland; UNL.) sought to find greater harmony between the approaches taken by different institutions to navigate these issues through policies and practice. They have sought to find more ways to navigate this. Legal departments in institutions have wanted greater clarity on the issue of who owns scholarly outputs. However, different institutions retain different preferences on copyright ownership and authors’ retention of publication rights.

Seeking productive solutions

Overall, institutional policy positions are complex, not uniform, and inconsistent. UNL has sought to apply a ‘typically Dutch approach’ to this complex situation, articulated neatly as:

‘Let’s talk, let’s try to solve it, let’s not give in.’

Based on a [recent report](#) of the 2022-2023 working group, each university is now seeking to clarify its copyright policies for all types of scholarly output and associated mechanisms to ensure authors retain appropriate rights. Some of them will publish their revised / elaborated policies early in 2025.

In 2025, a follow-up working group will look into possibilities for setting national policy and how to include this in the future collective bargaining agreement between universities and staff. First, they will seek to identify areas where there is little or no disagreement, and then where harmonisation may be possible, namely software and educational materials created by employees. They will also discuss what can be further

harmonised at a cross-institutional level. The group will then liaise with other stakeholders interested in this area - notably Universities of Applied Sciences, university libraries, and NWO, the national funder. A separate working group is also testing possible rights retention strategies, including one that complies with cOAlition S and NWO rules, for consideration by UNL's members.

NORWAY

All research institutions in Norway now have rights retention policies and are beginning to see their impact. The case study focuses on the University of Tromsø – The Arctic University of Norway (UiT), which now sees >96% of its researchers' journal articles made Open Access, with the rights retention policy instrumental in extending this to the approximately 20% of researchers for whom other routes are not viable. UiT's policy (and those in other institutions) has been well received by the research community and forms one strand of the institution's active pursuit of its strategy of being the Open Access pioneer of the North.

The importance of taking a stance

University of Tromsø – The Arctic University of Norway (UiT) adopted a policy incorporating Rights Retention on 1 January 2022. It was likely the first research institution in Norway or Scandinavia to do so, having been one of the earliest to have any kind of Open Access policy in 2010. Open Access became progressively stronger over time, and adopting rights retention elements was a further step in this direction. UiT is not, however, alone despite being an earlier adopter; at the time of writing, 20 organisations in Norway now have rights retention policies in place, including all the major research institutions.

For UiT, adoption was a policy response to funder requirements from the EU and the Research Council of Norway (RCN). The specific approach to rights retention was initiated by cOAlition S, within a wider set of goals for UiT. There was a strong desire to reduce the administrative burden on researchers and simplify the workflow followed to make research openly available via the institution's repositories. It was also aligned with UiT's strategy of being a progressive research institution supporting cutting edge Open Science practices.

The policy mandates that full-text versions of the Author Accepted Manuscript (AAM) or Version of Record (VoR) of all journal articles be made openly available in UiT's repository, currently called Munin. Those who wish to do so may apply for an exemption, but by failing to apply for an exemption, employees and students give the institution permission to make full-text versions available immediately under a CC licence – CC-BY for peer reviewed articles, CC-BY-NC-SA for Master's and Doctoral theses.

The Norwegian national Current Research Information System (CRIS) system, CRISTIN, which stores data and metadata on Norway's research activity, makes this approach viable. All Norwegian researchers are obliged to register their publications in CRISTIN, and encouraged or mandated (depending on their local institutional Open Access policy) to upload full text versions when doing so. Compliance with this is one factor that counts

towards institutional funding allocations. The backend of the Munin repository archive allows the updating of CRISTIN automatically.

The role of leadership

A key policy element is that UiT's Rector has assumed legal responsibility for interpreting and applying policy, resolving disputes and processing applications for exemptions. This is part of a deliberate strategy on UiT's part when launching and implementing the policy to demonstrate to researchers that the university supports them, and that they do not have to navigate the legal and policy requirements themselves. Research support staff and librarians are very active in supporting and communicating requirements to researchers and checking whether the publisher allows the Version of Record to be made available or whether an Author Accepted Manuscript is more appropriate.

This approach is echoed across Norway in other rights retention policies. UiT and other institutions sought input from legal experts when developing rights retention policies, and received advice ranging from curious to sceptical. Senior leadership and ultimately the Rector determined that the policy approach was sufficiently important and valuable to researchers to outweigh any perceived risks.

Response and experience to date

The response to the policy from UiT researchers has been relatively quiet, with only 3 opt outs being requested since January 2022. Near universal adoption has been facilitated by the proactive approach taken by library and research support staff to ensure all researchers upload articles and other written outputs. UiT had taken a low-key approach to engagement and advocacy, working with a group of internal champions made up of active researchers and engagement with local union representation.

There was some criticism at a national level due to an article in a research newsletter written by a copyright lawyer affiliated with 'Forskerforbundet', the Norwegian researchers' union. The author was critical of the rights retention approach and opposed to Creative Commons licences in principle, arguing that its advocates lacked knowledge about the legal position. However, this article was written after most policies were adopted with local union approval and almost two years ago. It was subject to strong pushback in writing from representatives of Norwegian institutions who had adopted rights retention and has not affected the course taken.

There has been no visible response from large international publishers. There are comprehensive Read And Publish agreements in place at a national level in Norway, but rights retention is proving important for reaching the long tail of researchers who publish in areas not covered by these agreements, around 20% of the total number of peer reviewed journal articles in 2022 & 2023. RCN had targeted 100% Open Access compliance by 2024. Although nationally that target has not been met, UiT has now reached >96% compliance with journal articles published by its

researchers, having reached 85-90% over a number of years previously. UiT is ahead of most other institutions in Norway with this figure, but its experience is not unrepresentative.

Rights retention is a part of the RCN strategy for the three-year period beyond 2025-2028 along with support for Diamond Open Access. This is reflected in the approach adopted by the largest local publishing entity, Universitetsforlaget / Scandinavian University Press ('The University Press') which relies heavily on public funds and is now moving many of its journals to a Diamond model while ensuring that remaining non-Open Access journals become compliant with rights retention and support deposit of manuscripts.

UiT has no active plans to review its rights retention policy. Any such review would be triggered if there were developments nationally or internationally that UiT identified that could be incorporated or that would require them to evolve their approach. The institution will, though, be working to create more viable Diamond Open Access options, leaving rights retention as a fallback position if alternative viable routes to Open Access are not available for researchers. Representatives from UiT continue to discuss rights retention with institutions and stakeholders in Sweden, Denmark, and beyond who want to take a more active stance. UiT emphasises that despite challenges and logistical risks, their approach has so far proved valuable to its strategy of being the Open Access pioneer of the North.

SERBIA

Under Serbia's copyright legislation, institutions hold economic rights to the outputs of publicly funded research for five years. Many institutions have adopted Open Access policies emphasising that this right allows deposit of research outputs into repositories. Institutions have also encouraged the use of author addenda. However, researchers often transfer rights to publishers, undermining these provisions. Legislation is under consideration to introduce a Secondary Publishing Right for researchers, but progress is slow and support is not yet widespread. Attention is also focused on strengthening the National Open Science policy by requiring authors to act in accordance with copyright law.

History of dialogue on rights retention

In Serbia, the enthusiastic promotion of rights retention dates back to 2018, particularly as part of the launch of the national Open Science policy (named "[Open Science Platform](#)"). There was awareness of the topic before this, but momentum picked up with the launch of Plan S that same year. At the time, there was insufficient capacity, interest or available resources to support Open Access, or for the Serbian national funder to consider joining cOAlition S. Nonetheless, Plan S still had a significant impact.

The 2018 Open Science Platform requires researchers to deposit a version of every scholarly publication (Version of Record or Author Accepted Manuscript) in the appropriate repository and make it available. It should preferably be publicly available immediately, but no later than after a 12-month embargo for STEM publications and 18-month embargo for Social Sciences and Humanities ones. There is no specific requirement for open licences. It also requires that institutions adopt green Open Access policies.

Not all institutions have followed this mandate, although many did, and some incorporated recommendations adopting the SPARC Author Addendum from 2006 to facilitate negotiations with publishers to achieve the mandate, although take-up of the Addendum was low.

This approach was pioneered by the Institute of Technical Sciences of the Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts, where the Electronic Information for Libraries (EIFL) Open Access Programme Country Coordinator for Serbia is the Librarian. Several other institutions have now followed that example, working notably through the Librarians' Section of the Association of Research Institutes of Serbia, founded in 2012. This operated as a community where members could learn together and compare experiences.

The EIFL Open Access Programme Country Coordinator, working as part of the Serbian Library Consortium for Coordinated Acquisition (KOBSON), coordinates training for researchers nationally, seeks to raise awareness and advocates for the benefits of retaining rights and aligning with the national mandate by making materials available through repositories rather than paying APCs. One study at the University of Belgrade showed that around 40% of researchers personally paid APCs. However, this figure might have

changed. APCs are now considered eligible costs by the national research funder if included in project budgets, and more Gold Open Access articles are now published.

Training also focuses on raising awareness of copyright law in Serbia, which needs to be better understood but offers a strong basis for rights retention. Under Article 97 of the Copyright Act, researchers employed at publicly funded organisations retain the moral rights to their publications. Still, the economic rights reside with the employing institution for 5 years. This allows institutions to deposit research outputs into their repositories without author permission or engagement. Researchers usually breach this law by transferring rights to publishers, but this practice is tolerated due to poor copyright awareness.

Legislative options

Even given the strong basis for institutional rights retention, further attempts at reform are underway. A Secondary Publishing Right is under consideration as an option by the Ministry for Science, Technological Development and Innovation, and there is engagement with KR21. However, there is a lack of interest from other parties, like the Intellectual Property Office, who would be critical partners in any such reform. Open Access is not well understood outside the Serbian research sector, and there has been opposition in the past at the national or institutional levels based on concerns that Open Access could threaten revenues generated from textbook licensing.

Instead, the focus has been on improving the national Open Science policy to strengthen it and add clarity. According to the updated Open Science Platform 2.0, adopted in December 2024:

“when signing publishing agreements, authors shall act in line with the provisions of the Law on Copyright and Related Rights that apply to work for hire and shall retain the intellectual property rights necessary to enable Green Open Access”.

The provision applies to all publication types. However, the policy still allows an embargo (3 months for STEM and 6 months for Social Sciences and Humanities), while the use of the CC-BY licence is not mandated, and the rights retention requirement will only be implemented after a delay, in 2026, to allow time for training and awareness-raising.

Such a solution is a result of challenging negotiations within the task force, where the feasibility of rights retention was questioned by representatives of research communities. Concerns raised include the fear that publishers may reject submissions containing rights retention clauses or delay publication, as well as that the workload for authors may increase. Challenges in managing situations where some co-authors must comply with rights retention requirements while others do not were also highlighted.

A representative working group, including librarians and researchers, worked on the wording of proposed changes, with input sought from the legal team at the Ministry. This does not guarantee that the recommended changes will be implemented, as there is strong pressure on researchers in Serbia to publish in high Impact Factor journals, and the Ministry is sensitive to this pressure.

Next steps

The reform project is well planned, and the engagement of different stakeholders will need to come at various points in different ways according to their motivations and roles in the process. This will include engagement with publishers, and it is hoped EIFL's experience in publisher negotiations will be available and valuable. The initiative intersects well with other work being done with non-commercial Serbian publishers to promote the use of CC-BY licences and to ensure authors are not required to transfer rights. A new national Current Research Information System will facilitate policy implementation monitoring.

SLOVENIA

Slovenia has adopted a comprehensive strategic and political framework for Open Science. The Scientific Research and Innovation Activities Act (2021) introduced legal obligations about retention of rights, which was extended by a governmental Decree on Open Science that set out a framework through which the Act would be implemented. An Action Plan for Open Science is providing financial and structural support for more effective implementation of principles of Open Science. As part of this Action Plan, the SPOZNAJ project aims to align research activities at the institutional level with principles embedded in Slovenian law. Different institutions are taking different approaches; notably, the University of Ljubljana, Slovenia's largest research institution, adopted an institutional policy that mandates authors to apply Open Science obligations in full. Further work to train and educate researchers, and legislative reform that would introduce Secondary Publishing Rights, are currently under consideration.

National strategic and legislative framework

Slovenia has adopted a comprehensive strategic and political framework for Open Science. This began in 2015 with the adoption of the [National Strategy on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Slovenia 2015–2020](#), complemented in 2022 with the [Resolution on the Slovenian Scientific Research and Innovation Strategy 2030](#).

These policies were accompanied by legislative reforms. The [Scientific Research and Innovation Activities Act 2021](#) introduced a top-down requirement to retain rights. In 2023 a governmental [Decree on the Implementation of Scientific Research in Accordance with the Principles of Open Science](#) ('Decree on Open Science') set out the framework required to implement rights retention, as well as other aspects of Open Science. It details what researchers and their institutions must do to comply with the requirement in Art. 40 of the Scientific Research and Innovation Activities Act which states that:

"...Open science shall include, in particular, open access to research results, the evaluation of the quality and impact of scientific research work using responsible metrics, and the integration and involvement of the interested public in the research process. More detailed requirements for conducting scientific research according to the principles of open science shall be set by the Government, taking into account the Scientific Research and Innovation Strategy of Slovenia and the recommendations of European research policies. Open science measures shall be defined in an action plan adopted by the Government."

The 'Decree on Open Science' is legally binding and very detailed. It was drafted by copyright experts working closely with the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation and a wider group of stakeholders, including representatives from research institutions. However, the Decree

on Open Science does NOT represent a reform of copyright law, but rather sets out how copyright of research outputs should be managed. This approach prevented issues arising from the side of the Ministry of the Economy, Tourism and Sport or the Slovenian Intellectual Property Office, which are rather conservative and can be resistant to anything that is perceived as a copyright exception.

The Decree on Open Science requires that authors of scientific publications (or their employers, where copyright is transferred to them by law) may only transfer copyright in scientific publications to third parties on a non-exclusive basis. It applies to research results that are at least 50% publicly funded, where 'research results' are defined as journal articles, monographs and other types of peer-reviewed publications, research data, and software. A CC-BY or CC-BY-SA licence must be used for journal articles, although CC-BY-NC or CC-BY-ND licences are permitted for monographs or other long-form publications.

Institutional policy support

The Decree on Open Science has only recently become law, and there is not yet a user-friendly explanation of the legal text in place to help understand the new regime in practice. This underlines the importance of institutional policy and institutional-level resources to complement the legal mandate and support, educate, and empower researchers.

This lies behind the launch of a national project on Open Science called 'Support for the Implementation of Open Science Principles in Slovenia' or [SPOZNAJ](#) (which means 'Learn' in Slovenian). SPOZNAJ is a part of the [Action Plan](#) for Open Science, a critical programme aimed at providing financial and structural support for more effective implementation of Open Science principles in Slovenia. SPOZNAJ includes 20 public research organisations, among them all public universities in Slovenia. It aims to align research activity at the institutional level with the Open Science principles embedded in Slovenian law, which includes provisions for rights retention but ranges more widely.

Different institutions involved with SPOZNAJ will adopt slightly different approaches. The University of Ljubljana (UL) is Slovenia's oldest public university and largest research institution and is a part of SPOZNAJ. It has actively considered the need to adopt a formal policy-based approach towards Open Science for at least five years. However, this did not move beyond including commitments in UL's annual plans to 'adopt Open Science principles', until SPOZNAJ was launched.

In March 2024, UL decided to mandate that authors cannot enter into contracts with an exclusive transfer of rights, and that all research outputs need to be publicly available under a CC licence immediately (without any embargo) after they are published anywhere. This mandate was transposed into UL legal rules from the national Decree on Open Science.

Further work to do

Reform in Slovenia is not finished. Further work is planned, including legislative reform and work to implement policies at the institutional level.

In 2024, the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation prepared the [Amending and Supplementing the Scientific Research and Innovation Activities Act](#) which would amend the Scientific Research and Innovation Activities Act 2021. The amendment would introduce Secondary Publishing Rights into the Slovenian legal framework, and would again be implemented outside of formal copyright law. The amendment proposes that researchers may publish their research outputs in a repository as soon as they have been accepted for publication. The amendment would also render null and void any contractual provisions that are contrary to presumptions such as this. The amendment is still in the process of adoption and is currently under parliamentary consideration, although objections have been lodged by the Intellectual Property Office.

Within institutions, there is a need for training and dialogue to accompany policies, to ensure researchers understand enough of their rights and their ability to use them. UL's size means that it will need to adopt an internal network or identify champions to raise awareness, something that it has recently undertaken successfully in the case of data stewardship.

THE UNITED KINGDOM

The N8 partnership of research-intensive institutions in the North of England was the first coalition of organisations to introduce rights retention policies in the UK, alongside a number of other institutions doing so individually in 2022 and 2023. The collaboration was rooted in existing structures that facilitated coordination of policies and activities across libraries. This allowed the institutions to move quickly when they may not have done so individually, to move at different speeds where necessary, and to pool support resources. Publisher reaction has been minimal and researcher adoption has been smooth due to the preparatory work done by the institutions. It is still early, but the policies appear to have had a measurable impact on materials being made Open Access.

Legal foundations

There has been a rapid development of institutional rights retention policies in the UK since 2022, founded on the work of the UK Scholarly Communications Licence and Model Policy (UKSCL) and a number of interested institutions. UKSCL undertook work and sought legal advice that demonstrated that British copyright law recognised a 'carve out' (that is, an exception or exclusion from a legal agreement or provision) that could be established where prior knowledge of a licence can be demonstrated, and that this could be applied to research outputs.

This meant that research organisations in the UK can assert a right to deposit articles by their researchers in repositories which cannot later be overridden by contracts that would otherwise assign exclusive rights to publishers. This applies so long the institution has appropriately publicised the policy and notified affected publishers.

This was the route adopted by Edinburgh University, Cambridge University, and some other early adopters who established policies and notified hundreds of publishers that they had done so. In parallel, they also undertook a range of consultations to engage and inform their researchers.

A wide range of other institutions reviewed this approach and considered the potential benefits it could have, and began to develop and implement similar policies themselves.

The N8 partnership

The N8 Research Partnership (N8) is a collaboration of the eight most research-intensive universities in the North of England. It was established in 2006 and consists of Durham, Lancaster, Leeds, Liverpool, Manchester, Newcastle, Sheffield and York. The partnership is a well-established collaboration operating at multiple levels, including in the advancement of Open Research. A collaborative forum of library directors has emerged from the partnership.

The library directors considered different options of how the N8 might collaborate on rights retention and drive this forward. A variety of different options were considered, with the process taking 18 months in total.

In the end, the institutions made a joint declaration in January 2023 'strongly recommending that researchers not by default transfer intellectual property rights to publishers'. The N8 was the first coalition to take a joint approach of this kind.

One declaration, but different flavours

A joint declaration was chosen because of the different contexts in which the individual institutions function. They operate at different scales, with different levels of research activity and funding. They have varying policy stacks on issues such as intellectual property and Open Access, and their internal decision-making processes are neither aligned, nor do they work on the same timescales. A joint statement ensured alignment across the institutions at an appropriate level, but allowed room for variation where it was necessary.

Within the N8, some of the institutions would likely have acted individually to develop and launch their policies without the collaborative initiative. However, not all of them may have done so, and none of them would have acted so quickly. By establishing a collaboration, the proposed policies had greater legitimacy than they would otherwise have had, and reduced the aversion that there might have been in individual institutions to the risk of acting alone.

Taking the [policy](#) of the University of York as an example, the 'Research Publishing and Open Access Policy' has rights retention as one aspect of the wider policy. The policy applies to staff who publish as part of their role. It covers journal articles and conference proceedings but not monographs or books. The use of a CC licence is expected (with a clear preference for CC-BY), but not mandated. The University's copyright policy previously allowed academics to sign away all their rights in publishing agreements, but as a result of the reform, the University retains a non-exclusive licence allowing it to upload manuscripts into an open repository, which takes priority over any subsequent agreement.

At Lancaster University, the relevant [document](#) is the 'Research Publications and Rights Retention Policy'. Its scope largely matches that of the University of York although it applies to all staff members of Lancaster University and postgraduate research students. It requires that researchers use a 'Creative Commons Attribution (CC-BY) licence.

The eight organisations worked collaboratively to develop and implement their policies. The process they followed mirrored that used by Edinburgh, Cambridge and other institutions. Each institution sought advice from different internal and external legal sources, and shared advice. An implementation group across the libraries was established with resources

put in place to share, for example, contact details of publishers, legal letters and any responses received, and support and guidance for researchers.

Responses and the future

The N8 initiative has seen little reaction from publishers so far. It is possible that there will be more of a response in 2025 when some large institutional deals across the UK are due for renegotiation, but to date this has not been the case. There was virtually no reaction to the letters institutions sent out, neither legal challenges to the policies nor any anecdotal reports of conflicts arising for researchers.

There has also been apparent acceptance from the individual institutions' research communities, who have readily adapted to the change with no pushback or negativity. The University of York reports that of the 81% of articles made Open Access in 2023 by their researchers, only 3% relied on the rights retention policy to do so. This is likely in part because the policies are still new but mainly because of the number of Read And Publish deals that have offered a seamless route to Open Access for many researchers. There has been no comparative review of how widely rights retention policies are being used across the N8 as yet, but more data will be collected and evaluated as policies come up for review in the next two to five years, according to the cycles at different institutions.

The joint declaration has helped to strengthen the already strong partnership between the N8. There are now greater connections between the Pro Vice Chancellors of Research and operational teams that supported the initiative. The network of library directors continues to consider future opportunities to collaborate and build on their work to date, with further collaborations on Open Research and the possible extension of rights retention policies to monographs or books.

Due to budget constraints, The University of York has exited from some Transformative Agreements (TAs) in 2025. In most cases, York will revert to individual journal subscriptions for highest use titles and mitigate the loss of 'read' access with document delivery, post-cancellation access rights and Open Access articles. Meanwhile, while the Library will continue to pay reasonable APCs in fully Open Access journals and continue [its support for Open Access models](#), there will be much greater reliance on the Green route to provide open access to AAMs in the institutional repository, [White Rose Research Online](#). However, when an institution does not subscribe to a TA, some publishers have submission systems and terms and conditions that seek to explicitly block or bypass institutional rights retention policies by routing authors to apply an embargo and not allowing CC-BY licences to be applied. University of York Library is pragmatically supporting authors through this process in the short term, while considering how to respond in the longer term. Resisting concurrent publisher attempts to establish new business models and revenue streams for Green Open Access may well require further collective action.

APPENDIX - METHODOLOGY

The research underpinning the case studies and this report consisted of 15 interviews with 20 individuals leading and participating in initiatives to increase take up of rights retention policies across 10 European countries, with a deliberate effort to include ones which have also already introduced, or are considering introducing, Secondary Publishing Rights. Interviews were semi-structured around a core set of questions covering set topics, alongside a number of additional follow-up questions that could be as necessary. Not all questions were used in each interview, and the approach varied depending on the context and the interviewees' existing policy knowledge.

STRUCTURED INTERVIEW QUESTIONS

The questions used to structure interviews were as follows:

Nature of initiatives

- Please could you describe the nature of the initiative in which you are participating.
 - What is the history/timeline of the initiative's development?
 - What are the initiative's intended outcomes?
 - Which stakeholders are involved?
 - Who does the initiative cover?
- What process did you follow?
 - What influenced the launch and development of the initiative?
 - What research was done / evidence was considered?
 - Who was consulted? Were researchers / authors part of the process?
 - Was there a legal expert involved in the consultation?

Particular regional circumstances

- What particular circumstances have you had to take account of when developing the initiative?
- How does the research funding and culture in the country or region affect the initiative?
 - What is the position of the national funding body or ministry? Is the political environment supportive? Is there a mandate for Open Access and the use of open licences?
 - Is there membership or strong influence of cOAlition S and other groups?
 - What are the key features of the publishing landscape? What is the nature and prevalence of Open Access and the use of open licences?
 - What are the key features of the research culture?
- What are the relevant laws and legal jurisdictions that you have had to take account of?
 - Including Secondary Publishing Rights and any legal advice influencing nature of policies
 - Is there a functional support system in the issues of IP management? How is it shaped and is it taking part in the initiative you are participating in?
 - According to the national regulations, how are works created by employees of the research performing organisations treated? Who has the right of exploitation according to the law, and how is it implemented in the tacit practice?
- What have been the major drivers of and challenges to progress?
 - Economic factors
 - Political climate
 - Cultural or social elements

Future developments

- What reaction have you had to the initiative and its implementation?
 - Publishers
 - International partners or peers
 - Authors and researchers
 - National/regional policy-makers and funders
- Do you have a timeline or roadmap for future developments or revisions?

- Do you consider your initiative completed?
- Do you have plans for further implementation?
- Have you set up (or planned to set up) a monitoring system?

Conclusion

- Is there anything that we have not covered or anything that you would like to ask before we finish the interview?

Following some of the interviews, additional details were sought, and a document review of materials recommended by the participants was conducted on an exception basis.

Interviews were recorded and transcribed using Otter.ai software, and used as the basis for the 10 case studies. These case studies were shared with interviewees and underwent a process of review to ensure that they were factually accurate and captured all relevant details. They were then reviewed by the Project Retain and KR21 national coordinators and experts.

Building Bridges to Open Access: Paths to Institutional Rights Retention in Europe 2024

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<https://sparceurope.org/>

Contact:
copyright@sparceurope.org

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Report authors:
Jon Treadway
Ignasi Labastida i Juan
Iva Melinščak Zlodi
Vanessa Proudman

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